

Deep exploration BoostEd by Advanced exploration Technologies

Data Management Plan

GA no.:	101177617
Document:	Data Management Plan / DMP
Deliverable	1.2
Summary	The DeepBEAT Data Management Plan (DMP) guides interdisciplinary data management throughout the project, ensuring research data aligns with the FAIR principles—findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable—while promoting Responsibility and Efficiency.
Version:	2
Author(s):	Anne Wollenberg, HZDR, project coordinator

Funded by the European Union under the GA no. 101177617. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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1. Data summary

1.1. Purpose and Relationship to Project Objectives

The data collected and generated during the DeepBEAT project will be essential for achieving its main objectives. In particular, it will support the development of cutting-edge geochemical technologies for the detection of deep land deposits using environmentally friendly, socially acceptable and low impact methods. In addition, the data will help promote public acceptance of exploration as a responsible and sustainable activity. By facilitating research analysis, partner collaboration and dissemination of results, the project ensures that its data are closely aligned with these objectives. Table 1 in Annex 1 provides an overview of the datasets that the participating organizations have generated or plan to generate as part of the DeepBEAT project. In addition, the DMP is a living document and Table 1 will be updated throughout the project. The next update is scheduled for March 2025. Table 1 in the annex provides an overview of the datasets that the participating organizations have produced or plan to produce as part of the DeepBEAT project.

1.2. Types and Formats of Data

Data are generated and managed within the research group in the following formats:

- Textual data: .docx, .txt, .pdf, .ascii
- Spreadsheet data: .xlsx, .csv
- Audio/Video data: .mp3, .mp4
- Web content: .html
- Geospatial data: .shp, .tiff
- Modeling data: .Rdata, .rds, .lfm (Leapfrog Model Files, possible to export to other data type formats for 3D modelling softwares)

1.3. Re-use of Existing Data

Where applicable, existing datasets will be re-used to enrich the research and ensure continuity. This approach not only saves resources but also ensures compliance with the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability). Data reuse ensures that research can continue beyond the end of the project, supporting further innovation in the field.

1.4. Estimated Data Size

The produced volume of data for the project DeepBEAT is estimated to be approximately 1 TB. This estimate does not include the use of existing data.

1.5. Potential usefulness of the data

The data generated is expected to be of significant value not only to the project team, but also to other researchers and companies working in related fields. By producing accessible, high quality research outputs, the project will ensure that the data support continued innovation in geochemical technologies and responsible exploration practices. This approach will enable researchers and stakeholders to build on the project's findings, further advancing the goals of sustainability and social acceptability in exploration.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Making the DeepBEAT data findable begins with the creation of metadata at the outset of data collection, which is stored as textual or spreadsheet data (see chapter **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**). Metadata for DeepBEAT includes standardised and structured characteristics that describe essential details about datasets, e.g. such as origin, purpose or creator. This metadata is essential for locating resources, providing searchable information to help users easily discover existing datasets, and providing a bibliographic citation record. DeepBEAT ensures the discoverability of data through the use of both descriptive and structural metadata, adhering to widely supported metadata standards that facilitate findability.

An exemplary structure of the minimum characteristics of metadata based on the IGSN is proposed below:

- Creator(s)
- Contributor(s)
- Year
- Dataset title
- Data repository or archive (e.g. Zenodo or Rodare): A persistent identifier (e.g., DOI or HANDLE) is assigned to publicly available data, ensuring it can be easily located, cited, and accessed, along with version and access details.
- Language
- Format
- Licence of use
- Level of openness/publicity, such as whether the data is open access, embargoed, restricted or available on request.
- Keywords to enhance the discoverability and comprehensibility of the data (where applicable)

- A short description of the data that makes the data understandable and helps re-users to assess whether the data meet their needs. The description includes what the data is about, where it comes from, how it was created, how it was processed, etc.
- Information of data set

In generating metadata, the project aims to follow the Ecological Metadata Language (EML) unified metadata description standard. To ensure that datasets are well organised and easily accessible, a standardised, logical and intuitive file naming convention will be used, such as described in Table 1.

Table 1: Naming convention for DeepBEAT data.

<p>The following naming convention should be used for datasets processed within DeepBEAT:</p> <p>DeepBEAT_WP_Task_(short)Name_Creator_Version_Modifier</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Example: DeepBEAT_WP1_T1.3_ContingencyPlan_HZDR_V1_LC</p> <p>Or</p> <p>DeepBEAT_Deliverable/Milestone_(short)Name_Creator_Version_Modifier</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Example: DeepBEAT_D1.2._DMP_HZDR_V1_BEAK</p>
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DeepBEAT supports the sharing of information across the consortium and recommends a uniform naming convention for all project-generated datasets (Table 2), ensuring that metadata is consistently applied. This enables team members and collaborators to easily find, manage, and access records when needed. By implementing these practices, DeepBEAT ensures that its datasets and metadata are properly documented, easily searchable, and ready for use and citation.

2.2. Making data accessible

DeepBEAT will generate data, some of which will be made publicly available in accordance with the principle of 'maximum openness with necessary restrictions'. Access to personal or sensitive data will be restricted. Each Work Package (WP) will process and analyse different types of data, including geoscientific information, codes, interviews and publicly available data. Most results will be published as project deliverables or in open access repositories (e.g. Zenodo), while respecting intellectual property rights (IPR). In line with the Description of Ac-

tion (DoA), deliverables and reports are primarily public, and selected elements may be archived with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI) to facilitate retrieval and citation. Sensitive data will be stored by the SharePoint cloud-based collaboration platform TEAMS hosted by BEAK (more information below).

2.2.1. Public access to data

Data and other publicly available outputs will be shared via open or trusted repositories to ensure open access in accordance with the grant agreement. When selecting a repository, DeepBEAT will aim to meet the following criteria

- Data can be assigned a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI or HANDLE)
- Public data will be released with a CC-BY licence or equivalent, if specific software or tools are needed to access or re-use the data, information about these will be provided in a complementary text file
- For the stored non-public data, the conditions for re-use (licence) are specified, under which these data can be accessed and requested.
- As defined in the Grant Agreement (GA), the data owner is responsible for determining the rights of use.
- Data and metadata will be accessible via a data repository, either publicly available, such as Zenodo or in-house repositories such as RODARE (measuring data) or GitLab (Codes).

DeepBEAT's Description of Action (DoA) also includes peer-reviewed scientific publications, which will be (1) submitted to open access journals for immediate access, (2) published under the most permissive licences, such as CC-BY, and (3) deposited in trusted archives or repositories (e.g. Zenodo or RODARE).

Project outputs and results will also be disseminated through various communication channels, such as the project website, conferences and social media, as detailed in the project's Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan (D5.1).

D5.1 will also include Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) for data and other outputs, which may require restricted access or prevent sharing altogether.

2.2.2. Internal access to data

The data collected and generated in DeepBEAT will be stored by the SharePoint cloud-based platform TEAMS hosted by BEAK, which is used by the project to manage, store and share documents and data. Original personal data will be stored primarily on the servers of the organisations collecting the data.

Access to these collaboration platforms is provided by the partner organizations, with access restricted to designated consortium members. Teams follows security best practices such as service level security through defence-in-depth, customer controls, and security hardening.

2.2.3. Handling and Publishing Personal Data

Personal data will be processed with strict safeguards to ensure fairness, transparency, accountability and confidentiality. It will only be collected as necessary for the project and will not include sensitive data.

Data from interviews, group discussions, focus groups, expert consultations and surveys are considered as personal data. The rights of research participants will be respected in accordance with ethical guidelines, EU and national data protection laws, and international human rights standards. Data collection, processing, sharing and disclosure will comply with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

If personal data need to be published, the following measures will be taken:

- Minimise the collection of personal data
- Anonymise or pseudo-anonymise data
- Publish aggregated data (e.g. summaries, spreadsheets).

Participants will be informed of their rights regarding their data.

Raw personal data, such as age group, nationality and postcode, from interviews and discussions will be handled carefully and stored on the partner organisation's secure server. Personal data will only be kept for as long as necessary: until the end of the project and if necessary for five years after data collection for research purposes.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Throughout the project, all data will be stored in formats that are easily accessible to other project participants, as summarised in chapter **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden..**

Public data will be made available in repositories/archives primarily in commonly used formats to ensure interoperability and reusability, most of which will be in text documents such as .docx, .txt, .pdf and .xlsx formats. Where appropriate, other data formats will be used, e.g. .mp3 for videos. Proprietary formats will not be used for publication, ensuring accessibility, transparency, and long-term usability of the content.

2.4. Increase data re-use

In order to ensure the re-usability of the data, guidelines will be developed where necessary. The use of standard privacy notices and consent templates will ensure a consistent approach to GDPR compliance (see 2.2).

Proper documentation is essential to ensure that data can be reused, both during the project and when it is made publicly available in a repository. This documentation will be included with the data where appropriate, for example as a read-me file. It should include a clear and thorough description of the data, including the methods used to collect and analyse it, the variables involved, and any relevant project information.

3. Other research outputs

No additional research outputs beyond the listed datasets in Table 1 in the annex are planned for this project.

4. Allocation of resources

DeepBEAT has not identified any specific costs related to data management between partners. The routine data management activities are covered in the project budget under salary costs. Additionally, equipment such as data repositories and archives, which are used to make data and other outputs publicly available, are either free of charge or provided by the partner organizations. External data sharing via the DeepBEAT website is included in the budget for WP5 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication activities.

5. Data security

In general, the IT Services of Partners BEAK is responsible for providing secure storage and HZDR additionally for backup services to those working on the project. In line with security best practice, backups are usually performed automatically on a regular schedule. It is also standard practice for project participants to use password-protected servers within their organisations to store data and other materials, ensuring that only authorised individuals have access. Data and other electronic materials are stored both within the project and within the partner organisations responsible for them.

6. Ethics

The participating organizations of DeepBEAT are dedicated to ensuring the adherence to fundamental EU values, including human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, and human rights. This commitment is in line with national, regional, and international human rights standards, such as the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols.

DeepBEAT's tasks and activities will be carried out in accordance with the highest ethical standards, ensuring compliance with relevant national, international, and EU laws, including ethical principles and the Horizon Europe rules for participation and dissemination (see also 2.2).

7. Other issues

Nothing to report at the moment.

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Data Management Plan

Deliverable 1.2

8. Annex A1: History of Changes of the DMP document

Table 2: Table of document modifications.

Name	Affiliation	Contribution / Review	Version
Anne Wollenberg	HZDR	Initial Version	1
Katarína Nagyová	LC	Review, Proposal Annex 2	1
Hafsia Munia	GTK	Review	1
Vojtech Wertich	CGS	Changes in Point 1.2 Types and Formats of Data, Changes in Annex A1+A2	2
Damith Agampodi	IMA	Changes in Annex A1+A2	2
Sándor Horvát	LC	Changes in Annex A1+A2	2
Matthew Leybourne	QUC	Changes in Annex A1+A2	2
Denise Baumann	SCI	Changes in Annex A1+A2	2
Hafsa Munia	GTK	Changes in Annex A1+A2	2
Kalle Penttilä	FCOY	Changes in Annex A1+A2	2
Andreas Knobloch	BEAK	Changes in Annex A1+A2	2
Jean Cauzid	UL	Changes in Annex A1+A2	2
Lotta Hanzelmann	ZL	Changes in Annex A1+A2	2

9. Annex A2: Overview of the expected contribution of DeepBEAT partners to the data repository

Partner: BEAK
What is the purpose / relationship of the data to the project objectives?
Beak will use available/existing legacy data from partners and other external stakeholders as well as newly acquired data for the modelling planned in WP3.
What types and formats of data will be generated / collect?
Mostly geospatial data in Esri ArcGIS format will be used such as vector (Esri Shapefiles) and raster data (Esri Grids). Secondly, for mineral prospectivity mapping, data will be stored in Beak's advanceo 2D and 3D Prediction software packages, which will use internal format for storage of data in folder structures. In addition, 3D models will be created and stored in either SKUA GOCAD or Leapfrog software packages and the related software formats. Besides this, general documents will be stored in Microsoft Office format as Word, Excel or PowerPoint files.
Where will it be stored?
Data will be stored primarily at safe data storage at BEAK data servers with is secured from external access and duplicated with the internal backup storage system.
Will you use any existing data and how will you use it?
Existing
What is the expected size of the data?
GB-TB
Who is the data shared with? Under what conditions? Who might benefit from the data (data users)?
Modelling results are being published in the deliverables and reports. Raw data from new sampling will be published in repository as part of WP3.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Repository of new investigation results from Task 3.2 and Task 3.3 will be submitted as Milestone M3.4

Partner: CGS
What is the purpose / relationship of the data to the project objectives?
CGS will collect and generated data needed to fulfill tasks of WP4 and collaborate with project partners within WP3.
What types and formats of data will be generated / collect?
Excel sheets (sampling points, coordinates, assays, sample databases, drillholes), SHP files for GIS softwares, georeferenced maps (Geo Tiff), photo documentation (JPEG)
Where will it be stored?
Databases, metadata storage of CGS, final datasets can be shared via platform agreed by DeepBEAT consortium.
Will you use any existing data and how will you use it?
CGS will use internal databases of Czech Geological Survey (various geology related datasets including geological maps, reports from past exploration/research, geophysical maps, geological profiles, lithochemical analyses etc.). CGS will use these data to plan sampling strategy, use them during field work and the data will be base for 3D modelling within the WP4.
What is the expected size of the data?
Hard to say in the beginning of the project, about 100 GBs perhaps. There will be a lot of interim data, the final datasets (results from analyses, geological models, maps etc.) that can be worth to share can have about 10 GB perhaps. But it is only rough estimation.
Who is the data shared with? Under what conditions? Who might benefit from the data (data users)?
Newly generated data will be shared with project partners to fulfill given tasks in WP3 and WP4. Results originated from new data or older re-processed data will be part of the deliverables and scientific journals as supplementary materials. Thus, these data will be publicly available and any other third party can benefit from it.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, the newly generated data (mineralogical, geochemical, isotopic data, 3D models, database of sampling points etc.) will be part of open science, after the publication in scientific journals (in open-access form).

Partner: FCOY
What is the purpose / relationship of the data to the project objectives?
FinnCobalt Oy is partner for DeepBeat consortium and has applied exploration permit to the Saramäki site.
What types and formats of data will be generated / collect?
Excel, access, word, shp, dwg, dxf, powerpoint
Where will it be stored?
FinnCobalt Oy stores its own data on physical servers provided by server provider.
Will you use any existing data and how will you use it?
FinnCobalt Oy uses the existing data for exploration purposes.
What is the expected size of the data?
< 1Tb
Who is the data shared with? Under what conditions? Who might benefit from the data (data users)?
FinnCobalt share geological data and exploration data with CEO and geologist.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
For this project FinnCobalt will not generate any sort of data, but if we generate some data, it could be shared publicly. Depending on the data.

Partner: GTK
What is the purpose / relationship of the data to the project objectives?
Collected data will be used to fulfill the various tasks outlined for WP2, contributing directly to the project's objectives.
What types and formats of data will be generated / collect?
Excel, word and powerpoint files for data storing, handling and reporting. Shape files for presenting and processing data in GIS. Geo tiff, video, maps for sampling planning and collecting.
Where will it be stored?
Data will be stored on GTK drive and shared consortium platform such as a dedicated Microsoft Teams channel.
Will you use any existing data and how will you use it?
Archive data from past exploration and research by GTK and relinquished data by companies (bedrock drilling and analyses, soil-till samples, aero- and ground geophysics) for defining appropriate mineral system model and 3D modeling of the deposit. For task 2.3, a free-of-charge digital elevation model (DEM) from the National Land Survey of Finland will be utilized. This DEM will be combined with data obtained through drone surveys to create a normalized digital elevation model.
What is the expected size of the data?
Archive data is some tens of GBs, and newly generated data is expected to be of a similar size.
Who is the data shared with? Under what conditions? Who might benefit from the data (data users)?
Both archived and new data will be shared with project partners. Results will be shared via deliverables and scientific publications. While project partners will have access to the full datasets, third parties will benefit through open-access publications.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, the newly generated data (mineralogical, geochemical, isotopic data, 3D models, database of sampling points, tree species crown and height maps etc.) will be part of open science, after the publication in scientific journals (in open-access form).

Partner: HZDR
What is the purpose / relationship of the data to the project objectives?
Collected data will be used to fulfill the various tasks outlined in the tasks 2.3, 3.3, 4.3 and 2.4, 3.4 and 4.4, contributing directly to the project's objectives.
What types and formats of data will be generated / collect?
.txt, .csv, .RData, .zip, .shp, .img
Where will it be stored?
Data will be stored on HZDR cloud system and shared consortium platform TEAMS (hosted by BEAK)
Will you use any existing data and how will you use it?
Stream sediment samples (WISTAMERZ), soil maps, snow + plant data from previous projects (also from different areas), public available geophysics data (magnetic, EM, resistivity, seismic)
What is the expected size of the data?
<1TB
Who is the data shared with? Under what conditions? Who might benefit from the data (data users)?
Shared with partners if requested, shared with scientist out of the research community of requested
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
yes

Partner: IMA
What is the purpose / relationship of the data to the project objectives?
Collected data will be used to fulfill the various tasks outlined for WP2, WP3, WP4, contributing directly to the project's objectives.
What types and formats of data will be generated / collect?
.docx, .txt, .pdf .xlsx, .csv
Where will it be stored?
In our own server and project server as needed
Will you use any existing data and how will you use it?
All the data will be novel
What is the expected size of the data?
< 5GB
Who is the data shared with? Under what conditions? Who might benefit from the data (data users)?
Shared with partners as needed and upon request, shared with scientist out of the research community of requested. Data may be shared with interested stakeholders.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, some of the data published in scientific journals and platforms will be part of open science.

Partner: LC
What is the purpose / relationship of the data to the project objectives?
LC will use data related to communication and dissemination materials to promote the DeepBEAT project and each partner that is part of the Consortium. LC will do so to maximize the dissemination of the Project activities and to involve stakeholders. Data related to the exploitation of the project results, and training materials will be created and stored as well.
What types and formats of data will be generated / collect?
Emails, Word documents, Excel sheets, PowerPoint presentations and images will be generated.
Where will it be stored?
On the cloud storage of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams), hosted by project partner BEAK and in our own server.
Will you use any existing data and how will you use it?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space should be less than 15 GB.
Who is the data shared with? Under what conditions? Who might benefit from the data (data users)?
Data will be accessible to partners of the project and interested stakeholders (e.g. website with partners presentations will be public, project brochure could be downloaded by interested users). The data might be useful for any stakeholders interested in DeepBEAT activities. Exploitation data will be accessible to granting authorities on request.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

Partner: QUC	
What is the purpose / relationship of the data to the project objectives?	Collected data will be used to fulfill the various tasks outlined for WP2, WP3, WP4, contributing directly to the project's objectives. Data will be used for PhD dissertation and associated publications.
What types and formats of data will be generated / collect?	Excel, word and powerpoint files for data storing, handling and reporting. Shape files for presenting and processing data in GIS. Geo tiff, video, maps for sampling planning and collecting.
Where will it be stored?	Data will be stored on Queen's data protected cloud services and shared consortium platform such as a dedicated Microsoft Teams channel.
Will you use any existing data and how will you use it?	Archive geochemical, geological, and geophysical data from the three WP sites will be used in conjunction with new data generated as part of the project.
What is the expected size of the data?	Archived data is ~ 10's of GBs, and newly generated data is expected to be similar.
Who is the data shared with? Under what conditions? Who might benefit from the data (data users)?	Both archived and new data will be shared with project partners. Results will be shared via deliverables, dissertation, and scientific publications. Although project partners will have access to the full datasets, third parties will benefit through open-access scientific and popular publications.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?	Yes.

Partner: SCI
What is the purpose / relationship of the data to the project objectives?
Data are used to support the project and show what is possible with our instruments.
What types and formats of data will be generated / collect?
Spectra and concentration data, csv/xlsx as well as pdf can be provided.
Where will it be stored?
Data are stored in a project specific folder and provided to the partners.
Will you use any existing data and how will you use it?
No usage planned from our side so far.
What is the expected size of the data?
Depending on the requests during the project.
Who is the data shared with? Under what conditions? Who might benefit from the data (data users)?
Data are shared with project partners of DeepBeat.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
If the provided data can/will be used is a decision of the partners.

Partner: UL
What is the purpose / relationship of the data to the project objectives?
A limited amount of new data will be produced in tasks W2.4 and WP3.5. Most data will be obtained from project's partners. The data processing will generate reports and codes.
What types and formats of data will be generated / collect?
New data will be produced as ascii files (.mca, .csv, .asc, .txt,...), processing will produce .xlsx, .docx and .py files.
Where will it be stored?
Data will be stored on UL drives and shared consortium platform such as a dedicated Microsoft Teams channel.
Will you use any existing data and how will you use it?
Data from previous projects and from in-house research will be used in DeepBEAT. That mainly consists in analyses of known minerals and part of it is already shared on the FAIR deposit ORDAR (https://ordar.otelo.univ-lorraine.fr/)
What is the expected size of the data?
Archive data consists in some Gb and the new data should be smaller than that.
Who is the data shared with? Under what conditions? Who might benefit from the data (data users)?
Data obtained from DeepBEAT partners will be ruled following the project Agreement. Data obtained during the projects and the processing results will be made available through deliverables and scientific publications, including data papers when possible.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Data obtained on samples that are not linked with IP issues (e.g. ore information) will be made available on ORDAR, a FAIR deposit and be linked with data papers either following the analytical procedures and data labelling from already published papers or be explained in new data papers.

Partner: ZL
What is the purpose / relationship of the data to the project objectives?
ZL is the owner of the lithium-tin-tungsten deposit in Zinnwald-Georgenfeld and has conducted extensive exploration and infill drilling. Therefore, the company possesses valuable physical and digital data to contribute to WP3 to derive the distal footprint of fertile granites, as the deposit is one of the largest in the area of interest for the DeepBEAT project.
What types and formats of data will be generated / collect?
No data will be specifically generated by ZL. However, ZL can provide access to physical data, such as drill core material and existing digital data sets.
Where will it be stored?
The digital data is stored on a physical server. The physical data is stored in the core shed of ZL.
Will you use any existing data and how will you use it?
-
What is the expected size of the data?
-
Who is the data shared with? Under what conditions? Who might benefit from the data (data users)?
The data will be shared with project partners (WP3) as needed and upon request. Decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis regarding whether entire raw data sets, partial data sets, or only processed data will be provided.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
-

10. Annex A3: Table of produced DeepBEAT Datasets

Table 3: Table of produced DeepBEAT datasets.

Name of Dataset	Site	Ownership	WP/Task	Responsibility	Generated via	Data Size	Format	Type of data	Sensitivity	Personal data	Delivery	Licence	Open Access